

International Journal of Advance Research Publication and Reviews

Vol 03, Issue 6, pp 610-616, June, 2026

Managers Leadership Styles and its Effect to the Efficiency of Management Process in Established Retail Store Businesses

Christine Joy A. Buan¹, Hazel A. Dela Cruz², Carlito Manlusoc³, and Angelo I. Mirador⁴

¹*Polytechnic University of the Philippines –Cabiao Campus*

²*Richard V. Gonzales*

chrisj.buan365@gmail.com¹, delacruzhazel@gmail.com², carlitomanlusoc@gmail.com³, miradorangelo77@gmail.com⁴

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.55248/gengpi.07.0626.16a41>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the correlation between retail store managers' leadership styles and the efficiency of management processes in established retail businesses in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. Using a descriptive-survey research design, data were collected from 100 employees across major retail establishments who had at least one year of tenure. The study focused on three leadership styles: autocratic, democratic, and laissez-faire, assessed against four core management functions: planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. Results showed that democratic leadership was perceived most favorably, with the highest weighted mean, and demonstrated statistically significant correlations with all four management functions, highlighting its effectiveness in fostering participation, open communication, and employee empowerment. Laissez-faire leadership also showed significant positive correlations, suggesting that employee autonomy can support management efficiency when staff are capable and self-directed. In contrast, autocratic leadership displayed weaker and, in overall terms, non-significant correlations with management process efficiency, indicating limitations of purely directive, top-down approaches in retail settings. The findings emphasize the need for retail managers to adopt adaptive leadership strategies that balance clear direction with participative practices. Recommendations for managers include implementing collaborative planning workshops, weekly team alignment meetings, employee recognition programs, and KPI-based performance tracking systems to strengthen planning, organizing, leading, and controlling functions. The study further suggests that future research should investigate situational or hybrid leadership models that can flexibly combine directive control with employee involvement, tailored to varying employee readiness and task demands. By offering evidence-based insights, this research aims to guide retail managers in enhancing operational efficiency and supporting economic dynamism in local communities like Cabiao, Nueva Ecija.

1. Introduction

Recognizing the role of being a leader is important in a business, as leadership is a well-known practice that has been used in a wide range of activities other than firms. Cribbin (1981) pointed out that leadership is a group of processes and steps that tend to influence the practices of organized people to accomplish the goals. However, leadership styles vary, and different approaches have diverse effects on a business. According to the study of Nguyen, P.V. et al (2020), entrepreneurial leadership is essential to raise the performance of firms. Business leaders, on the other hand, have the vision, skills, and experience to guide organizations to success. They are responsible for setting goals, developing and implementing plans, and motivating and inspiring employees (The Leaders Magazine, 2023, October). He or she is a person who leads the employees of an organization to collective success (Farland, 2023), and they are usually the CEO (chief executive officer), COO (chief operating officer), CFO (chief financial officer), president, and chair (Twin, 2024), business owners (Stone, 2024) and managers (Gupta, 2023).

A retail store is a physical or virtual establishment where businesses offer a selection of products or services directly to consumers for purchase (Gupta, 2024). On the other hand, as stated in *Cambridge University Press's* dictionary (2025), being "established" means to be accepted or respected because of having existed for a long period of time. According to De Sordi et al. (2024), a business must be operating for at least 42 months or 3.5 years, and as an additional criterion, an article online by *Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development* (2025) stated that a business must have a minimum of 10 employees to be considered as an "established" business. Meanwhile, a manager in general is one of the organizational leaders who oversees organizational activities (Sujan, 2024) towards efficiency and productivity (University of North Dakota, 2024). Thus, a manager plays a crucial role for the smooth flow of the management and operations, that can lead to its success. As stated by Cosin Consulting (2024), a store

manager's role is not just about the responsibility of running the store smoothly, but also in increasing sales. This person is responsible for optimizing the customer experience and managing the team. These responsibilities make the store manager a key element in the success of any retail business, thus making it in the market for a long period of time and being well-known and trusted by the local consumers.

According to the 2023 statistics of Gov PH, Cabiao, Nueva Ecija with a score of 0.2071 is ranked 222nd out of 511 Municipalities in the Philippines in terms of activeness of local establishments. This counts as one of the factors in the economic dynamism of Cabiao. The ranking for Cabiao is relatively low, and management process might be the sole reason for either winning or losing the market (Kaufmann, 2023). In parallel to this statement, leadership style is a key determinant of the success or failure of any organization. Leaders influence, direct, and motivate others to perform specific tasks and also inspire subordinates (Hambrick, 2007), supporting the *Classical Theory of Management* by Henry Fayol (1916), which suggests that managers must possess excellent traits in planning, organizing, leading, and controlling in order to achieve organizational efficiency and goals.

While extensive research has been conducted on various leadership styles and their effect on organizational performance, there is a noticeable gap in studies focusing specifically on the retail sector in the Philippine context, particularly in municipalities like Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. Most existing literature centers on large-scale enterprises or different geographical locations, leaving a void in understanding how leadership styles affect the efficiency of management processes in local retail settings. This gap underscores the need for a focused study that examines the correlation between managerial leadership styles and the efficiency of management processes within retail stores in Cabiao.

This study aims to investigate the effect of different leadership styles employed by managers in established retail stores on the efficiency of management process in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. By identifying which leadership styles are most effective in enhancing management processes, the study seeks to provide actionable insights for retail managers and business owners. The expected outcome is to develop a set of recommendations that can guide retail managers in adopting leadership styles that foster improved operational performance, employee satisfaction, and customer service quality. The study aspires to contribute to the economic development of Cabiao by enhancing the performance and competitiveness of its retail sector.

2. Research Method

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, descriptive–correlational research design. The descriptive component was used to assess employees' perceptions of their managers' leadership styles and the efficiency of management processes. The correlational aspect determined whether significant relationships exist between leadership styles (autocratic, democratic, laissez-faire) and the four major management functions (planning, organizing, leading, controlling).

2.2 Participants

The respondents consisted of employees from three established retail store businesses in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. Inclusion criteria required participants to be at least 18 years old and to have a minimum of one year of employment in the establishment. The retail stores included in the study met the criteria for being "established," operating for more than 42 months and employing at least ten workers. A total of 100 employees participated in the survey.

2.3 Instrumentation

The study used a structured survey questionnaire developed specifically to measure employees' perceptions of managerial leadership styles and the efficiency of management processes within established retail stores in Cabiao, Nueva Ecija. The instrument was designed to align with the objectives of the study and was divided into three major parts. The first part gathered the demographic information of the respondents, including age, length of employment, and work position in the store, which helped the researchers contextualize the participants' responses. The second part measured the extent to which managers displayed autocratic, democratic, and laissez-faire leadership behaviors, using a five-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree." The third part assessed the efficiency of the management processes, such as planning, organizing, leading, and controlling, using the same response scale. All items were constructed in a clear and concise manner to ensure that respondents could easily understand and accurately provide their perceptions based on their daily experience working under their store managers.

2.4 Validation of Instrument

Before the full administration of the survey, the questionnaire underwent a process of expert validation to ensure that each item was appropriate, relevant, and aligned with the study's variables. The researchers submitted the initial draft of the instrument to professional validators, who examined the clarity of the questions, the accuracy of the constructs being measured, and the overall suitability of the survey for academic research. Based on the feedback provided, several items were revised or refined to improve their precision and readability. After these revisions, a pilot test was conducted among employees from retail establishments not included in the actual study. The pilot testing via Jamovi software allowed the researchers to identify vague statements, estimate the time required for completion, and observe how respondents interpreted the items. The data collected from the pilot test were also used for reliability analysis, which confirmed that the instrument met acceptable internal consistency standards, with Cronbach's alpha values falling within a reliable range. This ensured that the final version of the questionnaire was both valid and dependable for measuring the study variables.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedures

To formally begin the data collection, the researchers first sought permission from the management of the selected retail stores by submitting an endorsement letter detailing the purpose and procedures of the study. After receiving approval, the researchers proceeded to personally distribute the survey questionnaires to eligible employees during their available work hours. Before answering the survey, respondents were briefed about the nature of the research, their rights as participants, and the assurance that their responses would remain confidential and used solely for academic purposes. The researchers guided participants through the instructions to prevent misunderstandings and allowed them sufficient time to complete the survey. For employees who were not present during the initial distribution, an online version of the questionnaire was provided to ensure full participation. Once all responses were collected, the researchers organized and encoded the data in preparation for statistical analysis.

2.6 Analysis of Data

The responses gathered from the survey were analyzed using several statistical tools appropriate for the descriptive-correlational nature of the study. Weighted mean was used to determine employees' level of agreement regarding their managers' leadership styles and the efficiency of management processes. The five-point Likert scale served as the basis for interpreting the verbal equivalents of the computed means. To examine the relationships between leadership styles and management process efficiency, the Pearson *r* correlation coefficient was employed. This statistical test allowed the researchers to determine whether increases or decreases in one variable were associated with changes in another, as well as the significance of these relationships at the 0.05 level of significance. All analyses were conducted systematically to ensure accuracy and to support the study's conclusions with empirical evidence.

3. Results and Discussion

This includes the detailed results and analyzation from the data gathered from 100 respondents of this study.

Table 1 Respondents' Level of Agreement on the Leadership Style of Their Manager

Respondents' Level of Agreement on the Leadership Style of Their Manager	WM	VI
Autocratic	3.65	Agree
Democratic	3.89	Agree
Laissez-Faire	3.65	Agree
Overall	3.73	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree; 4.21 - 5.00, Agree; 4.20 - 3.41, Somewhat Agree; 3.40 - 2.61, Disagree; 2.60 - 1.81, Strongly Disagree; 1.80 - 1.00

Table 1 summarizes the respondents' perception of their managers' leadership styles, ranked from highest to lowest based on weighted mean. Democratic leadership received the highest mean of 3.89, indicating that managers are perceived to encourage participation, delegate responsibilities based on team strengths, and promote open communication. Autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles followed with equal weighted means of 3.65, both still interpreted as "Agree." Overall, the findings suggest that while all three styles are present, democratic leadership is most favorably perceived and contributes more significantly to effective management in retail settings.

Table 2 Respondents' Level of Agreement on Retail Store Managers' Leadership Style Effect on the Efficiency of Management Process

Respondents' Level of Agreement on Retail Store Managers' Leadership Style Effect on the Efficiency of Management Process	WM	VI
Planning	3.96	Agree
Organizing	3.98	Agree
Leading	3.88	Agree
Controlling	3.89	Agree
Overall	3.93	Agree

Legend: Strongly Agree; 4.21 - 5.00, Agree; 4.20 – 3.41, Somewhat Agree; 3.40 – 2.61, Disagree; 2.60 – 1.81, Strongly Disagree; 1.80 – 1.00

Table 2 states that employees perceived their managers to be most effective in organizing tasks and resources, followed by planning, controlling, and leading. This indicates that managers were viewed as capable of clearly communicating goals, assigning tasks efficiently, monitoring performance, and motivating their teams. The strong ratings across all four management functions suggest that managers applied leadership approaches that supported coordination, structure, and consistent guidance. These findings imply that the leadership styles practiced in Cabiao's retail stores contributed to operational efficiency by reinforcing effective planning, organization, team leadership, and control within daily store operations.

Table 3

Significant Correlation Between the Respondents' Level of Agreement on the Manager's Leadership Style Towards the Efficiency of Management Process.

INDICATORS	P-VALUE	DECISION	CONCLUSION
Autocratic	0.07	Retain Ho	Not Significant
Democratic	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Laissez-Faire	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Overall	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant

Legend: If P-Value=<0.05–Reject Ho (Significant); If P-Value>0.05–Accept Ho (Not Significant)

Table 3 shows that democratic leadership ($p < .001$) and laissez-faire leadership ($p < .001$) had significant positive correlations with overall management efficiency, indicating that these styles were associated with better planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. In contrast, autocratic leadership ($p = 0.07$) showed no significant relationship, suggesting that a directive approach did not substantially enhance management efficiency in the retail stores

4. Conclusion

The results and discussion stated above detailed the following conclusions:

- 4.1. The respondents' level of agreement on the leadership styles of their managers in established retail store businesses has an overall verbal interpretation of "Agree".
- 4.2. The respondents' have an overall verbal interpretation of "Agree" towards the effect of managers leadership styles in established retail store businesses to the efficiency of management process.
- 4.3. There is a significant correlation between the respondents' perception of democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles and the efficiency of management processes, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. However, the null hypothesis was retained for the autocratic leadership style, as its correlation with management efficiency was not significant.

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, we give our deepest gratitude to **Almighty God** for granting us the strength, wisdom, and perseverance to complete our research study. His guidance and countless blessings made this journey possible.

We would also like to extend our sincere appreciation to our Research Adviser, **Richard V. Gonzales, MBA**, for his invaluable guidance, constructive feedback, and unwavering support throughout this research. His expertise and encouragement helped us stay focused and driven.

Our heartfelt thanks also go to the **Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Cabiao Campus**, our academic home, for providing us with a nurturing environment and resources essential for our study.

Special recognition goes to our Campus Director, **Engr. Fernando F. Estingor**, for his inspiring leadership and continuous support within our journey in making this research study.

We are profoundly grateful to **Dr. Jenny F. Estingor**, whose generosity in sharing her knowledge and answering our questions played an important role in helping us overcome the challenges of this study.

We would also like to thank our statistician, panellists, and everyone who contributed their time and expertise, helping us improve and refine our research.

Lastly, we are deeply thankful to our families, friends, and classmates, whose love, encouragement, and understanding gave us the motivation to persevere during difficult times. Their support served as a constant source of strength throughout our academic journey.

This achievement is a shared success, and to all who have been part of this endeavour, we are forever grateful.

- **C.J.A.B., H.A.D.C., C.M., A.I.M.**

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